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Identity Construction through Translanguaging in English Language Teaching: Teachers' and Students' Perceptions

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to investigate the role of Translanguaging in constructing identities of students through English Language Teaching. As a sample students and teachers of three universities were underscored : University of Management and Technology (UMT), University of Sialkot (USKT), Government College Women University Sialkot(GCWUS) . To uncover the role of translanguaging in identity construction of students, only one research tool was adopted: Interviews. 4-5 teachers and 5-6 students of English Department were interviewed from each University. Interviews were semi- structured and compromised of open-ended questions. Data was further analyzed qualitatively and subsequently findings were reported useful insights. In the light of findings, English language teaching through translanguaging has been recommended. This method is suitable to students of all backgrounds and construct students' identity positively.

Introduction

English language learning through translanguaging practices in a multilingual society like Pakistan is quite effective and useful method. In the multilingual society of Pakistan, the English language has slowly gained a symbol of social standard and a marker of prestige. English language proficiency has become the scale on which people are being judged, as its competence is directly linked with persons' novelty, modernism, intellect and societal position. Numerous individuals switch among English and native languages, whether its Urdu, Punjabi, Pashto, or others to gain acceptance and appear sophisticated. This consistent switching between languages represents the standard of English language in Pakistani society. Even if English language is such a priority and holds dominance, majority of the population lacks strong proficiency in the English. These processes have become increasingly common that it eventually becomes a part of classroom elements. However, learners definitely put a lot of efforts but still face confusion when exclusively communicating in English language. This confusion affects their confidence and their academic performance as well. So, translanguaging can be contributive factor in effective language acquisition. It fastens the process of language learning and also assists students in diverse aspects including their participation, confidence and their academic performances.

Even though it has multiple benefits regarding its contribution in fostering language acquisition and empowering learners are well-explored areas, still there is limited research on the translanguaging contribution in constructing students' identities in Pakistani ELT contexts specifically from dual perspectives of teachers and students. By including perceptions of both students and teachers, this particular research aims to fill this gap and provide its assistance in the emerging discourse of translanguaging as transformative practices.

In Pakistan's multilingual context, Urdu holds the status of the national language but English has been entitled as official language. In this linguistically diverse country, multiple languages such as Punjabi, Pashto, Sindhi, Balochi and Saraiki are widely spoken regional languages. British era marked as a turning point in the subcontinent because they established their rule. They acknowledged English language for

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

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economic and social purposes. They introduced the teaching of European literature and science in English language, and all allocated funds were utilized to promote English education. (Lord Bentinck, 1835). English serves as primary source to magnify individual identity and self-assurance. It is also being used to raise standards of education by adopting it as a primary source of teaching (Huang & Chang, 2024). Ghani (1999) asserted that English in Pakistan has attained great significance, particularly in the fields of higher education and white-collar employment. On a social level, it is regarded as a prestigious and polite medium of interaction among educated Pakistanis, and proficiency in English is often equated with being educated. As a second language, English has exerted a strong influence on both the economic and educational spheres of the country.

At the same time, while English remains a priority, it is equally important to maintain connections with national and regional languages. New pedagogical approach named *translanguaging* has been emerged as a tool to increase students' proficiency in more than one language. This encourages free switching between multiple languages at a time, using students' entire linguistic repertoire. Instead of strictly applying monolingualism, it encourages fluidly moving between languages. Garcia (2013) asserted that *translanguaging* meets at the intersection of languages and supports language abilities through incorporating productivity and respect for cultural background. *Translanguaging* has been raised prominent in field of Language acquisition and *Applied Linguistics*. In the systematic organization of educational field, *translanguaging* is being described as the utilization of one language as a catalyst to enhance comprehension and engagement in second language, resulting into cognitive development in both languages (Garcia, 2009). It is the pedagogical approach which helps learners to polish their multilingual skills by allowing them to use their full linguistic resources in classroom practices. This approach helps to build proficiency in weaker language by taking help from the dominant language.

Regarding identity, Baker (2017) has explained that identity is diverse and potent idea that defines the scale according to which students perceive their own selves and are being acknowledged by others. Identity is not static but continuously changing entity through societal conditions and personal experiences. Identity is often divided into multiple layers including personal, social and linguistic identity. Personal identity is based on a persons' intrapersonal relationship including intellect, self-opinion of life; social identity highlights inter-personal relationship involving group affiliation, societal interactions and cultural belonging; linguistic identity which is also being called as cultural identity expresses the effect of language and culture on individuals' identity. Hence, identity is not a stable or fixed entity but an ongoing identity negotiation process. Depending on the context, identity may be loaded with multiple layers. Such flexible nature of identity elaborates that it is sensitive to its environment with the presence of different individuals. Identity is crucial element in defining human beings and their interaction with the world. It represents the individuals' relationship with themselves. It affects every area of life such as Sociology, Linguistics, Psychology and Education, as it allows individuals to form meaning, relationships and place they hold in society. Identity has a strong and deep connection with language, because the manner with which humans select, utilize and negotiating among languages influence their way of looking at themselves. It also impacts the way they are being perceived by others. As *translanguaging* is a multilingual approach, so it serves students who have diverse linguistic background. In English

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

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Online ISSN: 3006-5895

language teaching classrooms, it directly influences students' identities as it supports full linguistic repertoire. It also constructs classroom environment into more equitable space, enabling students' identities into valuable assets. In this regard, following research questions have been generated:

What are teachers' perceptions of *translanguaging* as a pedagogical strategy and its role in students' identity construction?

How do students perceive the role of *translanguaging* in constructing their identities in English classrooms?

How does *translanguaging* contribute to a supportive and inclusive learning environment in English language teaching (ELT)?

Literature review

Translanguaging

The concept of translanguaging has been defined in multiple ways depending on scholars' philosophical orientations (Ambele & Todd, 2022). Ofelia García (2009) conceptualized translanguaging as the integration of diverse linguistic resources into a unified system, later extending it as a flexible and creative linguistic practice (García, 2013). The origins of the concept can be traced to Cen Williams, who observed the pedagogical use of Welsh and English in bilingual classrooms (García & Lin, 2017). Similarly, Li Wei (2017) defined translanguaging as a dynamic process in which languages function as an interconnected system, enabling knowledge construction through the full linguistic repertoire. From a pedagogical perspective, French (2020) emphasized translanguaging as a scaffold that enhances collaboration, conceptual understanding, and fluency. As a result, translanguaging has emerged as a significant approach in applied linguistics and multilingual education, contributing to both theoretical and practical dimensions (Cenoz, 2017), while also bridging the gap between home and school languages to promote inclusivity (García & Kleyn, 2016)

In the field of English Language Teaching (ELT), translanguaging is recognized as a powerful tool for enhancing both linguistic competence and identity construction. It facilitates comprehension of complex concepts, supports academic language development, promotes critical thinking, and fosters social and emotional growth (García, 2017). As a teaching principle, it encourages the flexible use of linguistic and semiotic resources to support plurilingual learners (Tai & Li Wei, 2021; Tai, 2020). Despite its advantages, certain limitations exist. For instance, teachers' lack of proficiency in students' home languages may hinder its implementation (McMillan & Rivers, 2011), highlighting the importance of teacher preparedness in multilingual classrooms.

The distinction between translanguaging and code-switching has also been widely discussed. Creese & Blackledge (2010) noted that while both involve language alternation, code-switching operate between separate languages, whereas translanguaging challenges the notion of linguistic boundaries. Li Wei (2018) further argued that translanguaging represents an integrated linguistic system rather than separate language practices. However, scholars such as Otheguy (2015, 2018) & Saraceni (2015) maintained that code-switching remains relevant for analyzing named languages from an external perspective.

Identity

Identity, as a dynamic and evolving construct, is deeply intertwined with language use. Language not only reflects but also shapes individuals' social and cultural identities. Ofelia García (2010) emphasized that language choice is central to identity negotiation in communicative contexts. Expanding on this, García and Wei (2014) argued that translanguaging creates opportunities for learners to reconstruct and balance their linguistic and cultural identities without abandoning any aspect of themselves. It provides a safe space for learners to position themselves within academic and social settings while negotiating their identities.

Furthermore, translanguaging plays a significant role in fostering hybrid and multilingual identities. Creese & Blackledge (2010) demonstrated that translanguaging practices enable learners to navigate cultural hierarchies and institutional expectations. García & Wei (2014) further highlighted its role in creating a "third space," a concept aligned with Bhabha (1994), where individuals construct fluid and dynamic identities. Classroom-based studies (Palmer et al., 2014) showed that translanguaging pedagogies—such as valuing hybridity and promoting metalinguistic awareness—empower students to explore and express their identities. Fatima et al, (2026) carried out a research on the reported practices in of Punjabi teachers while teaching English at primary school level of Sialkot and found it very useful for teaching and understanding of students of English language. On the other hand, Raman & Rubab (2025) explored the perceptions of university students' and teachers' practices regarding *translanguaging* in the classrooms.

In multilingual and postcolonial contexts such as Pakistan, translanguaging becomes particularly relevant. It enables learners to maintain connections with their cultural and ethnic identities while engaging with global languages like English. Scholars such as Canagarajah (2011) argued that translanguaging can challenge linguistic hierarchies and resist the dominance of English by validating local languages. Similarly, Hornberger & Link (2012) highlighted its role in fostering inclusivity and a sense of belonging. By encouraging students to draw on their full linguistic repertoire, translanguaging enhances participation, confidence, and identity expression (García & Kleyn, 2016). Overall, the literature demonstrates that translanguaging is not only a linguistic and pedagogical strategy but also a powerful means of identity construction. It enables learners to develop flexible, hybrid identities while actively engaging in multilingual practices, making it highly relevant for contemporary ELT contexts.

Theoretical Framework

The translanguaging theory views multilingual language practices as dynamic and fluid, allow individuals to use their entire linguistic repertoire to communicate, learn, and express themselves (García & Li Wei, 2014). Basically, this theory refers to using a speakers' entire linguistic repertoire without considering any linguistic boundaries. It is also considered as a pedagogical tool. Moreover, the sociocultural theory (Vygotsky, 1978) highlighted the role of social interaction, cultural tools and the environment in language learning and identity construction. Translanguaging theory aligns with this theory as it allows students to leverage their linguistic and cultural resources while engaging in meaningful interactions within social and academic contexts.

Research Methodology

Qualitative research methodology was adopted. Data was collected through interviews, conducted from students and teachers of English Department of three universities of Sialkot. Convenient sampling was implemented. Thirteen interviews from teachers and sixteen interviews from students resulted into total twenty nine interviews. Interviews were audio-recorded, then transcribed and converted into soft form. Two semi-structured interview forms were formulated for collecting the relevant qualitative data: one for students and other for teachers. Insights for constructing the interview forms were taken from translanguaging theory and identity construction in English language teaching (ELT) context. The items for interview forms were adapted from previous researches to ensure validity and reliability. Its alignment with the present study's objectives was also considered. Minor modifications were made for enhancing clarity, suitable wording and items within the focus of translanguaging practices and their role in the construction of students' identities. Data was analyzed by using NVivo software. This software provided the well-ordered association and interpretation of the collected data. By using thematic coding process of Braun & Clarke's (2006), data was generalized thoroughly and initial codes were created. Then themes were generated and child codes were assigned to every theme accordingly to facilitate refined meanings within the participants' responses. Various analytical features of NVIVO were employed to foster in-depth interpretation. These features include bar graphs, hierarchy charts, word clouds, word frequency table and comparison diagrams. These visual and statistical representations provided a more clear and authentic understanding of relationships and patterns that exist in data.

Data Analysis

Analysis of teachers' interviews

Questionnaire was comprised of items relating to teachers' attitude towards *translanguaging*, teachers' attitude towards students and their own teaching patterns. The questionnaire had 8 items in total. Following themes emerged out of NVIVO:

Figure 1: Hierarchy chart representing teachers' interview form

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

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Note: The NVivo chart visually represents the interview questions that were being asked from teachers and then on basis of teachers' responses, further themes and subthemes were organized. The diagram demonstrates how responses clustered around key ideas, showing the frequency and depth with which certain aspects of translanguaging and identity construction appeared in teachers' perceptions.

Theme 1: Empowerment and Voice through Self-Expression

This particular theme represents the personal identity construction of students and contribution of translanguaging practices in this process.

Code 1: Confidence Building

Switching between native languages and English reflects the solidarity, harmony and cultural identity accordingly. Two teachers have commented that:

"Yes, translanguaging helps students in constructing positive identity. They become more confident, their accent improves, their body language gets better, they feel layers of relaxation while speaking English."

"Students feel more confident and when they feel more confident, this contributes to their personal growth as well".

This opinion represent how translanguaging makes students more comfortable while communicating in English, further enhancing their confidence. This confidence improves their accent and makes them appear more sophisticated and presentable. Students' general capability to articulate ideas strengthens. Then students can confidently take part in any conversation that happens in their classroom settings whether its with teacher or their peers.

Code 2: Active Participation

When teachers are actually in a favor of translanguaging practices and encourages their students to communicative through translanguaging, this makes students to participate actively in classroom. Following are the statement of teachers:

"Yes, I do encourage. Because sometimes students are not comfortable with speaking English language. So, I allow them to communicate in translanguaging to reduce communication gaps."

"I encourage students because this is how students participate. I prefer students' participation a lot. So, I encourage them to use translanguaging. "

By evaluating these comments of teachers, it can be concluded that English is the legitimate code of English language teaching classrooms but when teachers embrace translanguaging approach, they can create psychologically safe environment in which mistakes of students are to be taken as a process of language learning. This is how the students who are deficient English speakers develop the confidence to actively participate.

Code 3: Articulation

The role translanguaging plays in allowing students to express themselves effectively and comprehensibly is no doubt crucial. This effects students' performance in their classrooms and construct positive identities.

"Obviously, they can express themselves better. Like this they can generate more ideas as well. Ideas are somehow connected to language so when a student tries to

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

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express his / her ideas in English language, which is obviously not their native language, they get confuse”.

This comment has revealed it helps students to overcome the fear of speaking and assists them to develop greater fluency and firm belief in their abilities. When teachers provide constructive feedback to students in classroom and don't take mistakes of students as an obstacle, it leads to the development of articulation in students.

Code 4: Vocabulary Limitations

Sometimes, the gap that exist in effective self-expression is students' poor vocabulary of English language because some concepts and terms are culturally specific and contextually dependent. Translanguaging aids them to fill this gap. As this teacher mentioned:

“Obviously students can express themselves more through translanguaging due to lack of vocabulary in English language.”

As revealed by this comment, translanguaging helps in effective communication. Students can articulate their ideas and emotions comprehensibly without any linguistic barrier. This would also let them be authentic, genuine and pure while reclaiming their places and voices in classroom.

Overall, from teachers' point of view, we can conclude that translanguaging empowers students and provide them emotional support. It transforms students into confident and extrovert beings by acting as linguistic empowerment tool. Students begin to perceive themselves as competent and efficient English speakers through developing confidence, better self-expression and active participation.

Theme 2: Construction of Belonging and Hybrid identities

Identity is socially constructed phenomena. Hybrid identities refer to the fluid identities which include multiple aspects of different languages and cultures. In ELT classrooms, students' hybrid identities cultivate by maintaining academic and linguistic boundaries.

Code 1: Cultural Legacies

Translanguaging encouragement by teachers is crucial element of students' hybrid identity construction in ELT classrooms as it helps to preserve cultural legacies and also develop English language proficiency. As mentioned by this teacher:

“ Yes, I encourage students to communicate in translanguaging. There are different points that are connected to using translanguaging in classroom. As our society is multilingual and languages are our legacies. To keep our legacies alive, we must speak these languages.”

According to this comment, when teachers encourage translanguaging in ELT classrooms, they indirectly cultivate pride, solidarity and respect for students' own culture and also makes the language learning process easier for students. This ultimately results into hybrid identities among students because students are learning target language while maintaining their emotional connection with their own culture (Garcia,2009).

Code 2: Splitting Lecture

Maintaining equilibrium between linguistic and cultural demands in ELT classroom

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

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could be achieved through multiple strategies.

"I create balance by dividing my lecture in two parts. In first half, I deliver lecture and in 2nd half, I give them different activities to improve their English skills."

"I do create balance by using translanguaging during topic explanation and give them tasks to write something in English."

This approach blocks all the linguistic barriers and preserves learners from being alienated. It allows students to adopt their culturally specific idioms, phrases, expressions and slogans into English language (Creese & Blackledge, 2010). This integration develops a sense of belonging in students because this is how they feel connected to their English language classroom and then ultimately such a balance leads to constructing hybrid identities among students.

Code 3: Story Narration

Strategy of narrating a story by using translanguaging, is valuable for making the students understand the difficult concepts and also assisting construct of hybrid identities in students.

"If I am discussing some story with students, I use translanguaging so that I can make students understand the concepts as well as maintain connection with their cultural."

Story telling can make realization among students about how knowledge could be diversified and can exist synchronically in multiple languages. Students can enhance their emotional connection with their cultural identity as well as increasing English language proficiency results into hybrid identities.

Code 4: Translation as Cultural Mediation

Sometimes teacher use translation method as cultural mediation, as it represents the ways how linguistic practices cultivate cultural identity within educational spaces. Few concepts that are difficult to understand in target language, teacher try to translate and comprehend them by taking help from native languages (Creese & Blackledge, 2010). As mentioned by this teacher:

"I create balance by translating and explaining difficult words of English that students are not familiar to. "

This comment of a teacher represents that when teachers value and declare students' linguistic background as permissible and constitutional resources of knowledge in ELT classrooms, they foster construction of hybrid identities among students. Such identities are negotiated somehow at the intersection of both languages.

Overall, languages are connected to cultural heritage and when teachers value students' cultural linguistics, they help to keep cultural legacies alive. This integrates sense of legitimacy and construct hybrid identities among students.

Theme 3: Translanguaging as a tool of cognitive identity construction

This very theme elaborates the intellectual identity construction of students through translanguaging practices. Teachers consider translanguaging as a pedagogical and cognitive strategy which allows cognitive flexibility in students identities.

Code 1: Analytical Insight

Students developing logical reasoning, clarity and comprehension results into strong analytical thinking. One of the teacher commented that: *"Through translanguaging,*

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

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students' cognitive development occurs. Translanguaging provides cognitive flexibility to students." Another said that: "Their knowledge increases; they become critical thinkers." One more said that: "They develop their own perspective."

Such perspectives of teachers reveal the capability of translanguaging that how it alters students' identities into active meaning-makers. It enhances learners' capacity to think analytically and systematically. It nurtures their independent judgment and fosters metacognitive awareness constructing them into opinionated individuals.

Code 2: Students' Comprehension

Teachers allow students to switch between languages so that comprehension barriers could be removed. It enhances their ability to acknowledge systemic or abstract ideas with clarity (Garcia & Li Wei, 2014). As one teacher commented this way:

"I encourage students to use translanguaging because it helps students to understand the concepts more clearly. When students discuss topic with teacher or with their peers and they use translanguaging, they can digest concepts more comprehensibly."

When Students communicate their ideas through translanguaging, it promotes their intellectual growth and communicative competence. Allowing linguistic flexibility redefines students' identities as highly educated and intelligent beings, enhances sense of competence among learners.

"Teachers' most important responsibility is to make students understand the topic, and students understand what is easy for them. For this purpose, translanguaging is very helpful."

Thus, with the process of transforming classroom settings into productive and dialogic place, it contributes in constructing students' identities in a way that they develop emotionally and cognitively (Garcia & Li, 2014). Students' credibility gets assured and aids in authentic communicative identity construction.

Code 3: Strategic Adaptation

Adopting effective strategies for the purpose of reaching the needs of students' learning process and for their active participation is crucial.

"At very start of my teaching journey, I only preferred English. So, students were not able to understand English well. So, with the passage of time, I shifted towards translanguaging strategy and I also encourage my students that they can communicate through translanguaging."

Beginning with students' home language and then gradually moving towards English language helps students to articulate ideas and foster communicative competence. Consequently, identity construction process strengthens by developing learners' competency.

Overall, translanguaging serves as a very strong and effective approach which enhances students' competence and analytical thought patterns. It helps to internalize abstract concepts accurately. Through deliberate implementation of translanguaging practices, students' identities become more knowledge based. This develops criticality and complexity in students thought patterns, resulting into intellectual beings, active knowledge recipients instead of becoming passive towards learning.

Theme 4: Translanguaging and Identity construction through Applied learning

Students' academic identities are being constructed through the academic rules,

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

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Online ISSN: 3006-5895

expectations and its way of operating translanguaging practices.

Code 1: Collaborative tasks

Flexible communication through translanguaging fosters intellectual development in students while group activities or any kind of peers' interaction. Students' interaction with each other improves their verbal expressions, intelligence and develops the skill of articulation.

"In my previous class, I gave them a group task in which they had to do discussion with their fellows. So, I instructed them to use translanguaging."

Experiencing such activities make students adopt the power and agency, as they are allowed to decide their own linguistic repertoire through which they can express themselves effectively.

Code 2: Performance Based Tasks

Performance based tasks such as making documentaries, roleplaying and vocabulary elaboration allow learners to express the information with more clarity through multiple languages. Different teachers commented that:

"I gave students a task to pick up different words of English from high school Grammar. Then write those words on white board and explain them in their native language."

"I gave students the task of role playing, in which they were supposed to use translanguaging."

"I gave them a task of making documentaries regarding different concepts. They were free to use translanguaging in those documentaries."

These tasks help them to increase their knowledge and competence. It portrays them as empowered and self-employed individuals. This reveals that negotiating translanguaging practices in a functional and productive manner develops empathy and leadership among students.

Code 3: Presentations

Human beings think through language, so it requires less effort to communicate in one's native language. Exclusively communicating in English language often creates confusion, limited interaction among students. Freedom of freely switching between languages reduces intellectual burden and escalates communicative confidence and competence.

"In last semester, students were giving presentations and they were bit uncomfortable doing it in only English. So, I allowed them to use translanguaging to give their presentation."

"Recently, students were giving presentations and were not comfortable in English language. So, I allowed them that they can use whatever language they are comfortable in."

Focusing these comments, activity of presenting in front of whole class becomes a tool for intellectual control. It results into individuals who are more self-controlled and have a sense of leadership.

Overall, students' academic identities can co-construct through such activities. These interactions allow them communicate flexibly and learning from each other's linguistic choices.

Figure 2: Word Cloud of Teachers' analysis

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

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Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Code 3: Demand of Degree

Few teachers discourage translanguaging because of the demand of students' degree and academic expectations.

"I don't encourage actually. Undermining the needs of their degree, they should be fluent in English and they have to attempt their paper in English language."

Adopting direct approach is no doubt productive and functional approach for escalating students' proficiency but it can exclude learners' identities from that learning space. It promotes a sense of confusion and tension for students.

Overall, Teachers' perceptions indicate that English dominant environment creating cognitive overload resulting into confused, resistant and fragmented identities among students

Theme 6: Teachers' Role in Mediating Identity Construction through Translanguaging Practices

This theme describes the teachers' personal priorities, perspectives on improving the translanguaging practices that could further enhance development process of students' identities in multilingual classrooms.

Code 1: Motivation and Support

Teachers inspire students to properly contribute by encouraging and guiding. This motivation and creating supportive learning environment construct confident, resilient and academically successful identities. Two teachers have argued that:

"Teachers should encourage and motivate students while valuing their cultural backgrounds. "

"Motivation is an important factor. Teacher should motivate students to learn English."

Code 2: Self Awareness

Teachers should must be aware of themselves first, that in which strategy they are comfortable.

"First of all, I think teacher should aware of himself that through which strategy he / she can deliver lectures more effectively."

Code 3: Suitable Environment

By providing a supportive and stimulating atmosphere, teachers can create a suitable environment which aids in positive identity construction with increasing proficiency of English language

"Teachers should create friendly environment so that they can feel free to ask questions and share some examples regarding he topic. "

Code 4: Students' Background

Valuing students' linguistic backgrounds in the ELT classroom acknowledges the diverse resources they bring to learning.

"Teachers should respect every students' linguistic background."

Code 5: Workshops

Academic institutions should must properly teach educators the strategic implementation of translanguaging practices, speeding up the process of identity

development

"There should be workshops to educate teachers about multiple teaching strategies in their classrooms."

Code 6: Policy Inclusion

Incorporating suitable policies in academic discourse for addressing the needs of language learning and fostering the positive identity construction is crucial.

"Translanguaging should be a part of our policies. It should be part of our academic policies."

Code 7: Independent Learning

Practical activities for learning process empowers students to learn language independently and develop a sense of ownership.

"Students should be given topic on which they have to speak for few minutes. They should be given time to brainstorm ideas regarding topic and then speak about it. I think this is the best way to improve students' competence."

Overall, suggestions provided by teachers reflects their self-awareness regarding the reaffirming attitude of translanguaging strategy and its role in constructing positive identities.

Analysis of Students' Perceptions

This section reports the findings with reference to identity construction of students in English language classrooms. Following themes are emerged out of NVIVO:

Figure 3: Hierarchy Chart representing the interview form of students

Note: This hierarchy chart was extracted from NVIVO software. It visually represents the students' interview form. The chart represents students' experience, personal beliefs, and attitude towards translanguaging practices and their perspectives of how could it effects students' identity. Students' illustrations inspired six themes that

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

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highlight different dimensions of students' identities. Students' responses represent the coherent relationship of language and identity. When languages shift, identity also gets shifted. in multilingual educational contexts.

Theme 1: Development of Linguistic Competence and Identity Construction

This particular theme represents the development of confident, competent communicative identities among students. Linguistic flexibility enables students to better develop their vocabulary and communicative competence. Students' identities get deeply embedded in linguistic improvement and better self-expression, resulting into the ability of articulation.

Code 1: Communication Skills

When students are allowed to communicate freely irrespective of any language, they can experiment their linguistic choices. Through these experiments, students can develop the confidence which leads to better communication skills (Garcia, 20019). As one participant noted

"My communication skills has been improved a lot whether it's with a teacher, class fellow or with any other person. "

Similarly, another remarked:

"Our identity gets groomed. Because teacher him/herself is speaking more and more English. So, students try to copy their teachers. My communication skills have been improved a lot. I can deliver my point of view more effectively. "

With the aid of first language, students develop competence in English language. This competence increases their social interactions. This self-confidence can lead to their academic and professional success.

Code 2: Vocabulary

By involving students' native languages, English vocabulary could be improved drastically as they can translate the word into their first language and learn it according to its context. As one student reflected,

"My vocabulary has been improved drastically."

Students may become passive towards learning but translanguaging solves this problem by promoting free linguistic practices and helps students to improve their pronunciation and vocabulary.

At times, the pressure to align with dominant language norms, such as prioritizing English, can alter one's manner of expression, self-presentation, and even interpersonal relationships. Thus, translanguaging and language choices play a significant role in the ongoing construction and negotiation of identity.

Code 3: Gradual Improvement

Slowly and gradually learning English language through translanguaging is an effective approach because it allows students to proceed step by step. As one student explained,

"Yeah, it helps. Because through translation in Urdu language we can improve our English. Learning new English words and using them in our conversations slowly and gradually improve our English"

Students develop the sense of self as a competent, brilliant individuals. Students as evolving multilinguals develops the quality of persistence and adaptability. Their

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

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linguistic competence enhances very slowly and naturally, resulting in full immersion of language in mental framework of learners and strong communicative identity.

Code 4: Simplified Language

Students revealed that teachers should use simple English, so it would be easy for students to comprehend meanings. It fastens the language internalization process, reduces linguistic barriers and construct confident identities. One participant suggested,

“Teachers should speak English but they should use easy wording so that students who don’t have enough knowledge regarding English language can learn it.”

This perspective showed that simplified language is crucial for weak English speakers. Communicating in common English with association of native language of students is suitable for every student of classroom, resulting into inclusiveness in classroom. Students feel confidence, and empowerment when they perceive themselves linguistically secure.

Overall, Translanguaging facilitates communicative identity which is linguistically competent and expressive. The process of shifting from one language to another simultaneously, empowers fluent and authentic selves. Freedom of linguistic choices helps learn to portray their identities as bold, fluent and authentic.

Theme 2: Emergence of Self-Efficacy as a Foundation for Empowered Action

This particular theme identifies the construction of students’ personal identity. It empowers students on multiple steps and evolves a sense of agency among within academic settings.

Agency and voice

Learning English language makes students develop confidence, which is the most prominent change that develops in humans’ personality. Linguistic flexibility enhances sense of comfort.

“I can confidently speak in English without hesitation.”

“Before coming to university, I was more introvert person. But with passage of time due to translanguaging practices my English-speaking skills have got better and I have become an extrovert person.”

“I can handle any situation with more confidence now.”

Students become more expressive, articulate individuals which serves them in their every sphere of life. Students’ transformation from being introvert, hesitant to confident beings highlights stronger identity, leads to agency and solid self-belief.

Code 2: Peers Support

Attitude of peers also play a significant role in identity construction. Students feel empowerment, sense of belonging and supported in such classroom environment.

“Students have relatively positive attitude because they also use translanguaging.”

Students start to engage and participate more actively and confidently during language journey without facing any judgement.

Code 3: Teacher as a Role Model

Role of teachers in constructing students’ identities is highly prominent whether it is about raising efficient or dumb learners of English.

“Teachers should display themselves as an example and should give students

different tasks to improve their language.”

Teachers should display themselves as an example to determine whether to empower or restrict student identities. Students try to imitate their teachers by taking initiative and actively participating. Translanguaging as a pedagogical approach develops agency in students, they start to perceive their identities as contributive instead of just being observer of learning process. Students try to imitate their teachers by taking initiative and actively participating. Overall, students undergo high cognitive development. Students experience of multiple linguistic systems cultivates mindfulness, maturity and criticality in their thought process.

Theme 3: Cultivation of Cognitive Growth and Intellectual Selfhood

This particular theme defines the cognitive development among students, which is one of crucial elements of identity construction.

Code 1: Mindfulness and Maturity

Cognitive development involves the progressive enhancement of mental processes such as thinking, reasoning, and problem-solving.

"This gave me new perspective as well."

"Before coming to university, I was little confused but now my thinking has become clearer. I have developed the quality of mindfulness. "

With the help of translanguaging, students' understanding towards learning deepens. Communicating through multiple languages require more sharp mind activity which empower their interpretive and analytical mindset.

Code 2: Criticality

Translanguaging encourages critical thinking skills in students because students can freely participate and question the strategies and interpret meanings according to their contexts.

"I have developed more critical thinking skills"

"I have developed problem solving skill. "

Students evaluate knowledge more consciously when allowed to continuously shift between languages. This kind of engagements allow them to compare, contrast, critique and learn language with ownership.

Code 3: Transitions across Educational Levels

Students revealed that when they move from school to college level, this movement bring transitions in educational patterns. These transitions empower students' intellectual and cognitive growth because students need to put lot of efforts.

"As in college, English was not that much hype. But in university, teachers prefer more English. So, I started adding more and more sentences of English in my communication. As this change is sudden but it cultivates cognitive and intellectual development."

As students struggle to fulfill the demands of institutions, they construct their identities from being simple language learners to critical and active participants.

Code 4: Task Based Activities

Task Based activities plays crucial role in learning language through practical implementations. Learners apply knowledge productively and creatively by implementing it in social interactions.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

"Teachers should give different tasks to students."

Such collaborative and practical tasks develop sense of ownership and decision-making skills. By engaging students into deep observing process, students learn to interpret and construct knowledge consequently.

Theme 4: Reaffirmation of Cultural and Linguistic Heritage

This particular theme describes the construction of hybrid identities among language learners. It explores the ways through which translanguaging encourages students to cherish their linguistic and cultural identity as well as balancing with the globally accepted identities. This maintaining balance somehow results into hybrid identities (Bhabha H.K. 1994).

Code 1: Sense of Belonging

Developing English speaking skills fosters a strong belonging in students for academic settings. It provides them validity, acceptance and confidence among peers and in social places as well.

"Biggest change I feel is that I have developed a sense of belonging. Others use English, so I also speak English to act cool. "

Students' linguistic choices in translanguaging contexts are strongly associated with their sense of belonging (Garcia, 2009). It increases their harmony with their academic contexts. Thus, with the help of translanguaging students develop strong sense of belonging with their classroom environment.

Code 2: Linguistic background

Teachers should be well-aware of students' linguistic backgrounds and teachers should show sensitivity towards it. This sensitivity directly influences students' identities.

"Yes, teachers have positive attitude towards translanguaging and value students' linguistic background. Teacher encourages and motivates students to improve their English language through translanguaging."

"In very first semester, one of my class fellows was not good in English. But teachers supported her and encouraged her a lot. Due to this, her communication skills have been improved a lot."

Every learner come from different background and being respected by their English language teachers foster hybrid identities. This reaffirmation of their cultural identity in English language classrooms results in dual personality.

Figure 4: Bar Graph representing the percentage coverage of Students responses regarding the impact of translanguaging practices on Students' identities

Note: Students' interviews highlighted the role translanguaging plays in constructing students' identities.

Code 3: Mixed Peers Attitude

Students' partial encouragement of translanguaging plays a crucial role in constructing hybrid identities. It creates a open space for students, maintaining cultural heritage as well as fulfilling linguistic demands.

"Students do prefer English but they also have positive attitude regarding translanguaging."

"Some are in a positive view of translanguaging but prefer English language only"

As mentioned by students, this flexible approach arises open and bold identities, resulting into developing confidence for cultural identity and motivation for academic and social success. Translanguaging validate, associate and improve their self-expression by acting as a bridge in academic settings.

Code 4: Situation Adaptability

When students adopt their linguistic choices on the basis of audience and context, it represents their deep internalization of language rules. This situational adaptability reflects fluid nature of their identity.

"Yes, I feel more comfortable in translanguaging while expressing my emotions. But in formal situations I prefer English only. "

"It depends on the person I am talking to. I use translanguaging around my friends but while communicating with teacher, I automatically switch to English language."

Such situations influence how students managed their language use, often forcing them to balance self-expression with peer acceptance. This balance fosters hybrid and flexible identities among students.

Overall, Translanguaging serves as a bridge between tradition and modernity, allowing students to sustain their cultural and linguistic heritage while engaging with global academic communities. These mediation approaches foster hybrid and dual identities in students.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Theme 5: Identity Tensions and Linguistic Power Dynamics

This particular theme represents tensions and confusions faced by students while learning English language.

Code 1: Instructor Mood

As mentioned earlier, that teachers' attitudes and behaviors leave drastic effect on students' personalities. Ultimately the students' success, empowerment and restrictive identity, all are depending on teachers' behavior.

"Depends on teachers' mood. If teachers' mood is good, they allow us to freely switch between languages but if they are not in good mood, they restrict us to use English only."

Code 2: Gender based Differences

Students stressed on the gender biased differences that exist among their language teachers. Translanguaging encouragement and discouragement often depends upon the gender of the instructor.

"It varies from gender to gender. Male teachers bound us to speak English only and female teachers are supportive and use translanguaging in classroom."

These gender biased differences that exist among teachers reflect that how agency and power dynamics contribute in identity construction of students. It diminishes their confidence and participation.

Code 3: English as a Standard

Students strongly emphasized on the treatment of English language as a standard and marker of prestige in Pakistani society and academic settings as well.

"Teachers take English language not as a language but as a standard."

"There is a superiority complex in our class that is connected to English language speaking. Everybody thinks that speaking English is cool thing to do."

"People impose English on themselves."

This symbolization of English language as a standard makes students abandon their native languages and their own culture, resulting into conflicted identities.

Code 4: Judgment

English language is to be staged as measuring scale of class, success and rank in society. Students are being judged so strongly which results in students conflicted identities.

"Everybody prefers English language. So, the pressure to fit in with peers was a challenge for me."

Such practices can make students question their own identities, resulting into internal security and limited confidence.

Overall, translanguaging aids as an empowering tool but it also exposes students' attitudes towards it. Such attitudes promote frustrated and conflicted identities.

Theme 6: Reimagining Translanguaging Pedagogies for Holistic Identity Development and Linguistic Growth

This particular theme represents the suggestions and improvement methods which are mentioned by students.

"Our education system and syllabus should be improved. "

" We are expected to speak English only and most of students are not good at English. Also, we don't have a proper setup of learning English systematically. "

As students asserted that well- organized curriculum design should not just confined to English grammar or it's vocabulary, it should involve it's use in academic and social settings. Students naturally perform well if teachers and institute values students background and also help construct positive identities accordingly.

Overall, suggestions provided by students reflect the need of harmonical, effective and balanced strategy of learning English language and implementing translanguaging into the process of positive and strong identity construction

Figure 6: Comparison of Students' and Teachers' Suggestions for Improving Translanguaging Practices

Note: The diagram (extracted from NVivo) provides a comparative representation of students' and teachers' responses regarding suggestions for improving translanguaging practices in English Language Teaching (ELT) classrooms. It visually highlights how both groups, while addressing the same theme, focus on different yet complementary aspects of improvement.

Findings

Translanguaging could benefit in diverse ways if implemented well. Participants stressed its role in positive and encouraging classroom environment. When teachers value students' home languages, it leads to identity affirmation and self- assurance. Translanguaging bridges the gaps that exist within multilingual discourse.

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Translanguaging intentionally and unintentionally creates an inclusive environment among students that motivates them to express themselves authentically and without having a fear of judgment. It allows students to have a sense of relief and perceive their identities as asset. Teachers mainly highlighted that their contribution in creating a supportive and positive environment is crucial. When teachers showcase that they respect and value students' home languages, they promote translanguaging approach as a pedagogical and legitimate strategy. Students further highlighted that translanguaging stimulate collaboration and shared insights among them, as it reduces communication gaps that happens due to varying proficiency levels. It fosters comprehension and group interaction, which results in inclusivity and mutual respect. In such positive classroom environment, students' proficiency in English language improves as well as their intercultural empathy and cooperation escalates

Conclusion

In conclusion, translanguaging surpasses all boundaries and customs that exist in linguistic systematic organization, prioritizing the development of single repertoire without consideration of any strict rules. This idea of implementing translanguaging practices into English language teaching classrooms does not follow stereotypical educating methods but rather promote societal equity and helps to construct identities of students in diverse ways. It aids in eliminating the traditional hierarchies and construct hybrid identities among students. Additionally, translanguaging helps to develop confident, empowered and intellectual beings. This creates a broader way of language perception, developing creative and authentic language users. Teachers and students both perceive translanguaging as the analytical, confident, productive and pivotal way to implement their entire linguistic repertoire and construct positive identities among students.

Future Research

Future researches can elaborate and demonstrate this study in diverse ways. Unveiling translanguaging by examining it at both primary and secondary educational levels can contribute effectively in existing literature of translanguaging and identity construction in English language teaching classroom.

References

- Ambele, E. & Watson Todd, R. (2022). Translanguaging patterns in everyday urban conversations in Cameroon. *International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, 2022(273), 181-197. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijsl-2020-0118>
- Bhabha, H.K. (1994). *The Location of Culture* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203820551>
- Canagarajah, S. (2011). Translanguaging in the classroom: Emerging issues for research and pedagogy. *Applied Linguistics Review*, 2, 1 - 28.
- Cenoz, J. (2017). Translanguaging in School Contexts: International Perspectives. *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*, 16(4), 193–198. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15348458.2017.1327816>
- Chen, X, Li, J. & Zhu, S. (2021). Translanguaging multimodal pedagogy in French pronunciation instruction: Vis-à-vis students' spontaneous translanguaging. Vol: 101, Page: 102603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2021.102603>

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

- Creese, A., & Blackledge, A. (2010). Translanguaging in the Bilingual Classroom: A Pedagogy for Learning and Teaching? *The Modern Language Journal*, 94(1), 103–115. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25612290>
- Fatima, S., Rubab, I. & Mirza, M.S. (2026). Translanguaging: Perceptions and Reported Practices of Punjabi Teachers of English. *Journal of Applied Linguistics & TESOL*. 9 (1). Jou
- Hornberger, N. H., & Link, H. (2012). Translanguaging in Today's Classrooms: A Biliteracy Lens. *Theory into Practice*, 51(4), 239–247. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23362829>
- García, O. (2011). *Bilingual Education in the 21st Century: A Global Perspective*: Wiley.
- García, O. and Wei, Li. (2026). Translanguaging. In *The Encyclopedia of Applied Linguistics*, C.A. Chapelle (Ed.). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781405198431.wbeal1488>
- García, O. (2017). Translanguaging in Schools: Subiendo y Bajando, Bajando y Subiendo as Afterword. *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*, 16(4), 256–263. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15348458.2017.1329657>
- García, O., & Kleyn, T. (Eds.). (2016). *Translanguaging with Multilingual Students: Learning from Classroom Moments (1st ed.)*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315695242>
- García, O., & Lin, M. Y. A. (2017). Translanguaging in bilingual education. In O. García, A. M. Y. Lin, & S. May (Eds.), *Bilingual and multilingual education* (Third edition ed., pp. 117-130). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-02258-1_9
- Mateus, S. G. (2014). Translanguaging: Language, Bilingualism, and Education: Ofelia García and Li Wei. (2014). New York, NY: Palgrave MacMillan, 162 pp. *Bilingual Research Journal*, 37(3), 366–369. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15235882.2014.965361>
- McMillan, B.A. & Rivers, D.J. (2011). The practice of policy: Teacher attitudes toward “English only”. *System*, 39(2), 251–263, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2011.04.011>.
- Tai, K.W.H. (2021). Translanguaging as an inclusive pedagogical Practices in English Medium Instructions Science and Mathematics Classrooms for Linguistically and Culturally Diverse Students. *Research Science Education*, 52, 975-112. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-021-10018-6>
- Otheguy, R., García, O. & Reid, W. (2015). Clarifying translanguaging and deconstructing named languages: A perspective from linguistics. *Applied Linguistics Review*, 6(3), 281-307. <https://doi.org/10.1515/applirev-2015-0014>
- Otheguy, R., García, O. & Reid, W. (2019). A translanguaging view of the linguistic system of bilinguals. *Applied Linguistics Review*, 10(4), 625-651. <https://doi.org/10.1515/applirev-2018-0020>
- Ramzan, T. & Rubab, I. (2025). Exploring University Teachers' and Students' Perceptions on Translanguaging Practices in English Classrooms. *Kashf Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(3), 25-37. <https://doi.org/10.71146/kjmr>
- Saraceni, M. (2015). *World Englishes: A Critical Analysis*. Bloomsbury Publishing Company. <http://www.bloomsbury.com/uk/world-englishes-a-critical-analysis-9781623562632/>

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

- Saraceni, M. (2010). *The Relocation of English: Shifting Paradigms in a Global Era*. Palgrave Macmillan UK.
- Palmer, D.K., Martínez, R.A., Mateus, S.G. & Henderson, K. (2014), Reframing the Debate on Language Separation: Toward a Vision for Translanguaging Pedagogies in the Dual Language Classroom. *The Modern Language Journal*, 98: 757-772. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12121>
- Wei, Li. (2018) Translanguaging as a Practical Theory of Language. *Applied Linguistics*, 39 (1) pp. 9-30. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amx039>
- Wei, L., Hua, Z., & Simpson, J. (2023). *The Routledge Handbook of Applied Linguistics: Volume Two*: Taylor & Francis.
- Williams., C.R. (1994). Arfarniad o ddulliau dysgu ac addysgu yng nghyd-destun addysg uwchradd ddwyieithog.